

UNDERSTANDING THE GLOBAL GOAL ON ADAPTATION: THE ROAD FROM DUBAI TO BELÉM

UPDATED TECHNICAL
BRIEFING FOR COP30

I. Introduction

The **Global Goal on Adaptation (GGA)** was established by the Paris Agreement ([1/CP.21, Article 7](#)) as a global goal of enhancing adaptive capacity, strengthening resilience, and reducing vulnerability to climate change, with a view to contributing to sustainable development and ensuring an adequate adaptation response in the context of the temperature goal.

Operationalization of the GGA began with a two-year Glasgow-Sharm el-Sheikh work programme launched at COP26 ([7/CMA.3](#)). It continued with the adoption of the UAE Framework for Global Climate Resilience at COP28 and the launch of another two-year work programme, the UAE-Belém work programme 2024-2025 ([2/CMA.5](#)).

ADAPTATION IS A KEY GLOBAL CHALLENGE FACED BY ALL

In November 2024, at the midpoint of this new work programme, **Parties came together at COP29/CMA6 in Baku to negotiate key elements for 2025 and beyond**, resulting in [decision 3/CMA.6](#). Main areas of negotiations included:

- The process of indicator development and timeline for the work up to COP30/CMA7.
- Guidance to the Chairs of the SBs and experts on methodologies, approaches, and criteria.
- The mandate of experts to develop new indicators.
- Transparency of the work of the experts.
- Expected outcome and outputs of UAE-Belém work programme (size and nature of indicator list, mode and scope of indicator aggregation, any additional outputs).
- Collaboration between experts groups and linkages or synergies across thematic and dimensional targets.
- Representation of different regions and groups as well as gender balance among the expert groups.

This technical briefing offers a concise overview of the current state of GGA negotiations ahead of COP30/CMA7 in

Belém, including summarized information on how Parties, experts, and other actors have been working to develop indicators and address a range of cross-cutting and emerging issues.

Operationalizing the GGA is a technical as well as political task, and different actors are playing different roles towards accomplishing it. Parties drive the negotiation process, but the convened experts as well as constituted bodies, especially the Adaptation Committee (AC), have supported or are supporting the technical work.

As a **standing agenda item**, the GGA will continue to be discussed beyond CMA7 in Belém, including at SB64, CMA8, and subsequent sessions.

COP: Conference of the Parties to the UNFCCC

CMA: Conference of the Parties serving as the meeting of the Parties to the Paris Agreement

SBs: Subsidiary Bodies, including the Subsidiary Body for Scientific and Technological Advice (SBSTA) and the Subsidiary Body for Implementation (SBI)

Defining the concept of adaptation

Adaptation describes the process of “**adjustment to actual or expected climate change** and its effects in order to moderate harm or take advantage of beneficial opportunities” (IPCC AR6 WGII) as well as the outcome of said process. It can pertain to biophysical, economic, socio-cultural, or environmental practices, methods, or assets, and take place in an **incremental or a transformational** manner. Other characteristics of adaptation action include timing (anticipatory, concurrent, reactive), intent (autonomous or planned), scope (local, national, regional, global), and ownership (public, private).

II. The state of play before Belém

COP28 saw the adoption of the UAE Framework for Global Climate Resilience (hereinafter referred to as “Framework”) to “guide the achievement of the GGA and the review of overall progress in achieving it, with a view to reducing the increasing adverse impacts, risks, and vulnerabilities associated with climate change, as well as to enhance adaptation action and support.” The Framework also established **seven thematic and four dimensional targets**, and Parties launched a second work programme on the GGA. In 2024, Parties then agreed on the **timeline for the remainder of the UAE-Belém work programme up to CMA7** (November 2025), which was further updated at SB62 in June 2025.

Figure 1: Timeline of the GGA work programmes

As per decision 3/CMA.6, the Framework is due for **review after the second Global Stocktake** in 2028, allowing Parties to include learnings from the application of indicators and assessment of progress towards the targets. The terms of reference for the review are yet to be developed, and Parties decided to initiate deliberations on this area after the completion of the UAE-Belém work programme, including through the Baku high-level dialogue on adaptation.

Figure 2: Targets under the UAE Framework for Global Climate Resilience

III. Developing indicators for the GGA

78 experts convened

Compilation of ≈ 10,000 indicators

List of 490 indicators prior to SB62

Final list of 100 indicator options

The UAE-Belém work programme on indicators has the aim to identify (and, as needed, develop) **indicators and potential quantified elements "for measuring progress achieved towards the targets."** After SB60, a mapping and compilation of existing indicators was conducted based on [submissions from Parties and non-Party stakeholders](#) (5,304 indicators) and [indicators reported in Parties' national reports and communications](#) compiled by the AC (4,639 indicators). The SB Chairs [convened 78 experts](#) across all targets nominated by Parties and other actors to assist in the technical work based on Parties' guidance.

Based on the [refined indicator mapping published after the October 2024 workshop](#), experts have worked to refine and develop indicators following CMA6. After the submission of reports from all expert groups, the Secretariat has compiled a [consolidated list of 490 indicators](#) and published a [report by the technical experts](#) and a [technical report on indicators](#).

At SB62 in June 2025, the **experts were invited to reduce this consolidated list of indicator options to no more than 100** while taking into account the additional guidance provided (see figure 4). A meeting of experts was held in August 2025 to verify the columns for metadata and data collection, verify that indicators are in line with the guidance given, undertake a peer review, and conduct quality control checks. Following this, the [final list of indicator options](#) was submitted by the experts and published by the Secretariat together with a [technical report by the expert group](#), including information on methodologies, data availability, and disaggregation.

Figure 3: Breakdown of final list of indicator options (and compared to pre-SB62 list)

Figure 4: Criteria for the refinement of GGA indicators

SB60 criteria for indicator mapping

([FCCC/SBSTA/2024/7](#), para. 41, and [FCCC/SBI/2024/13](#), para 79)

- (a) Relevance to measuring progress
- (b) Specific relevance to adaptation
- (c) Quantitative or qualitative
- (d) Data availability
- (e) Ability to reflect regional, national, and local circumstances
- (f) Applicability across different contexts
- (g) Ease of interpretation
- (h) Clarity of associated methodologies across contexts
- (i) Ability to be aggregated and disaggregated
- (j) Basis on best available science
- (k) Basis on traditional, Indigenous, and local knowledge
- (l) Not to be used as a basis for comparison

Additional criteria for possible consideration

([Decision 3/CMA.6](#), paragraph 17)

Parties agreed that the **key criterion for the indicators is their specific relevance to adaptation**. However, they also invited the experts to consider the other criteria presented here.

SB62 additional guidance for reducing and refining the indicators

([FCCC/SBSTA/2025/4](#), para. 51, and [FCCC/SBI/2025/11](#), para 96)

(a) Phrase indicators as measurable indicators rather than statements	(f) Include qualitative narratives to explain context behind quantitative statistics
(b) Refine indicators that describe impacts, exposures, or hazards without capturing adaptation relevance	(f) Include qualitative narratives to explain context behind quantitative statistics
(c) Make existing indicators derived from other conventions and frameworks adaptation-specific	(g) Sub-indicators should capture various contexts of adaptation action
(d) Remove indicators for measuring climate change mitigation	(h) Indicators for MoI and other enabling factors are to be included
(e) Include indicators that capture adaptation responses to risks and impacts associated with different warming scenarios	(i) MoI indicators are to measure access, quality and adaptation finance, including provision, in line with the Paris Agreement

Expected final outcome in Belém

As decided at CMA6, **the final outcome of the UAE-Belém work programme may include the following:**

- A manageable set of no more than 100 indicators that (a) are globally applicable, (b) constitute a menu that captures various contexts of adaptation action, and (c) enable assessment of progress towards the targets and their different components.
- Information on the intended purpose of and potential data sources for the indicators.
- A source of input for the technical phase of future Global Stocktakes.
- The outcome should be consistent with Article 7.1 of the Paris Agreement and the temperature goal referred to in Article 2 of the Paris Agreement.

IV. Cross-cutting and emerging aspects

While targets and indicators are at the core of the GGA, negotiations and technical discussions have also focused on a range of cross-cutting aspects. This includes, inter alia, means of implementation; linkages to other processes, such as the Global Stocktake (GST); National Adaptation Plans (NAPs); Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs); the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC); and a range of cross-cutting considerations relevant to several or all of the targets.

In addition, concepts such as different adaptation approaches and transboundary adaptation could be explored by Parties and through the work of the Secretariat, constituted bodies, and experts.

Mol Means of implementation

The New Collective Quantified Goal on Climate Finance (NCQG) noted with concern the **gap between climate finance flows and needs, particularly for adaptation**, as well as the need to dramatically scale up adaptation finance. CMA5 recognized that means of implementation are crucial for implementing the Framework, and CMA6 decided that the final outcome of the UAE-Belém work programme should include, where applicable, **quantitative as well as qualitative indicators for enabling factors for the implementation of adaptation, including means of implementation** (finance, technology transfer, capacity-building), to be developed, as needed, or identified from the compilation and mapping.

GST Global Stocktake

CMA6 decided that the final outcome of the UAE-Belém work programme should constitute **a source of input to the technical phase of the GST**, by specifying a way to structure and inform the assessment of progress in adaptation. The second GST is scheduled for 2028, followed by future GSTs every five years thereafter to assess collective progress towards meeting the goals of the Paris Agreement.

NAPs National Adaptation Plans

As noted in the CMA6 decision, **NAPs are one of the important channels via which the targets could be achieved**. However, there is a need to provide guidance to Parties on how to integrate the targets and indicators into their NAPs and particularly the monitoring, evaluation, and learning (MEL) components, which would be especially relevant for targets 10 (b) and (d). The Least Developed Countries Expert Group (LEG) has developed [updated technical guidelines for formulating and implementing NAPs](#), which attempt to unpack the GGA targets and reference GGA-related considerations under recommended contents of the NAP, highlighting that the GGA provides a framing for adaptation at the national level.

IPCC Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change

As the **United Nations body for assessing science related to climate change**, the IPCC has been invited to collaborate with the SBSTA Chair to organize a special event at SB62 to provide an update on the work of IPCC Working Group II, which assesses climate impacts, vulnerability, and adaptation options. The CMA6 decision also references the upcoming revision of the “IPCC Technical Guidelines for Assessing Climate Change Impacts and Adaptations” including adaptation indicators, metrics, and methodologies, which will be published as a separate product in the IPCC’s seventh assessment cycle.

In addition to the specific elements and processes listed above, there are also **broader cross-cutting considerations relevant to several or all of the targets**, as well as a need to enhance collaboration and synergies across the thematic as well as dimensional targets. The CMA5 and CMA6 decisions outline a wide range of such considerations:

- Gender (2/CMA.5, para 13, 3/CMA.6, para 21)
- Participatory and fully transparent approaches (2/CMA.5, para 13; 3/CMA.6, para 21)
- Human rights approaches (2/CMA.5, para 13; 3/CMA.6, para 21)
- Intergenerational equity (2/CMA.5, para 13)
- Social justice (2/CMA.5, para 13)
- Vulnerable ecosystems, groups, and communities (2/CMA.5, para 13)
- Children, youth, and persons with disabilities (2/CMA.5, para 13; 3/CMA.6, para 21)
- Education and empowerment (2/CMA.5, para 23; 3/CMA.6, para 21)
- Indigenous, local, and traditional knowledge systems (2/CMA.5, para 14; 3/CMA.6, para 15)
- Science-based and guided by best available science (2/CMA.5, para 14; 3/CMA.6, para 35)
- Social inclusion (3/CMA.6, para 21)
- Indigenous Peoples (3/CMA.6, para 21)
- Migrants (3/CMA.6, para 21)
- Health of children and young people (3/CMA.6, para 21)

Other cross-cutting areas for consideration could include the **role of constituted bodies and other entities**, including the AC, the LEG, the Facilitative Working Group (FWG) of the Local Communities and Indigenous Peoples Platform (LCIPP), and the Nairobi Work Programme (NWP); the **potential role of non-Party stakeholders** and other actors, such as official statistical bodies; **dialogue between Parties, experts, and other stakeholders**; and the **exchange of knowledge, experience, information, and best practices** pertaining to the targets (for example, at Adaptation Forums or UNFCCC Climate Weeks).

Figure 5: Other concepts of potential relevance to the GGA

V. Unpacking the SB62 informal note

At SB62, Parties were not able to conclude some parts of their discussions due to lack of time, including on potential elements that could be included in the CMA7 decision. Parties agreed to continue their engagement at SB63 and CMA7 based on [an informal note that reflects their initial discussions](#) on key aspects of the GGA, including draft elements of the decision text.

The potential elements of the CMA7 decision on the GGA can be divided into four sections covering (1) the GGA indicator package, (2) the Baku Adaptation Roadmap, (3) adaptation approaches, and (4) other provisions.

(1) GGA indicator package

This section of the decision may encompass recalling the different and relevant mandates and outcomes on GGA from past CMA decisions. Additionally, it may also shed light on providing the context to operationalize the indicator package. The operative part of this section of the decision would be primarily focused on adopting a GGA indicator package and set out provisions for how indicator work can be utilized by Parties at national level as well as within relevant processes under the Paris Agreement, such as the GST, Biennial Transparency Reports (BTRS), NDCs, NAPS, Adaptation Communications, and National Communications. This section could also identify or mandate constituted bodies or SBs to undertake further work related to the GGA.

(2) Baku Adaptation Roadmap

Decision 2/CMA6 in 2024 launched the Baku Adaptation Roadmap (BAR), which is aimed at advancing progress in line with Article 7.1 of the Paris Agreement and supporting the implementation of the elements outlined in paragraph 38 of decision 2/CMA.5. The BAR is anticipated to play a central role in post-Belém work related to the GGA and provide a forward-looking framework that enables enhanced action, coherence and support for adaptation efforts at all levels. Scaling up adaptation action and support is a priority in this regard, particularly for developing countries. The informal note contains a total of eight different options for the BAR and how it could fit within the wider institutional architecture for adaptation.

(3) Adaptation approaches

The discussion on adaptation approaches (such as incremental and transformational adaptation) is informed by the IPCC AR6 WGII, which included the concept. Parties have debated its relevance and discussed if these should be included in the decision, as well as the value of highlighting specific adaptation approaches over others.

(4) Other provisions

This section contains potential provisions related to the adjustments of MEL systems and identifying capacity-building needs; the role of NAPs; the engagement of relevant stakeholders; how to feature outcomes of the Baku High-Level Dialogue on Adaptation; a proposal for a new adaptation finance goal to succeed the Glasgow pledge; and a review mechanism with a timeline for future work.

VI. Means of implementation

Decision 3/CMA.6 decided that **the final outcome of the UAE-Belém work programme should include “quantitative and qualitative indicators for enabling factors for the implementation of adaptation action, including Mol.”** SB62 further invited the experts to include “indicators for Mol and other factors that enable the implementation of adaptation action,” remove “those that are not relevant to the Paris Agreement,” and use Mol indicators “to measure (1) access, (2) quality, and (3) adaptation finance, including provision, in line with the Paris Agreement, to help Parties address needs and gaps.”

The experts responded to this mandate by including a column in the template for the final indicator list that marks relevance of the indicator to (i) Mol and other factors that enable implementation or (ii) other enabling factors, as well as another column marking relevance to the three aspects of measurement.

Table 1: Targets with indicators relevant to Mol as tagged by the experts in the final list

Target	Indicator	Mol relevance	To measure...
9(b)	9b03	Capacity-building	
	9b05	Finance	Adaptation finance
9(g)	9g06	Capacity-building	
10(a)	10a10	Finance	Access, quality, adaptation finance including provision
10(b)	10b03	Finance Capacity-building	Adaptation finance including provision
10(c)	10c05	Finance	
	10c06	Finance	Access, quality, adaptation finance including provision
	10c07	Finance	Access
	10c08	Finance	Quality (option 1), adaptation finance including provision (option 2)
	10c09	Technology	
	10c10	Capacity-building	
	10c11	Capacity-building	

As per the technical report prepared by the experts, the second part of the indicators grouped under target 10c on MoI apply to all targets and should be seen as cross-target indicators that can be disaggregated by thematic targets,. Due to the political nature of discussions around MoI, the experts have proposed multiple options for three of these indicators (10c06, 10c08, and 10c09) for further consideration by the Parties.

Table 2: Cross-target indicators relevant to MoI as summarized by the experts

Finance	Technology	Capacity-building
1 indicator on cost of adaptation actions	2 indicators to capture institutional dimension of capacity building through tracking existence of institutional arrangements for adaptation training	1 indicator to measure degree of implementation of Parties' identified adaptation technology needs
1 indicator on amount of international public finance for climate change adaptation		
1 indicator on annual adaptation finance expenditure	1 qualitative indicator on extent to which capacity building interventions lead to increased adaptive capacity	
1 indicator on private sector finance related to adaptation		

Beyond these cross-target indicators, **targets 9(b), 9(g), 10(a), and 10(b) have their own indicators for means of implementation (MOI) and other enablers of adaptation**. The experts clarified that MOI are specifically reflected under target 10(a) to enable access to early warning and climate information, given the nature of the target and its activities.

In addition to MoI being a critical consideration across all thematic targets and in relation to the dimensional targets, there are also **potential interlinkages with other UNFCCC processes and mechanisms**. These interlinkages range from climate finance discussions (including the NCQG and a new adaptation finance goal to succeed the Glasgow Pledge) to relevant cross-cutting considerations, such as equity, inclusion, rights-based approaches, or vulnerable groups and ecosystems.

VII. The path ahead: CMA7 and beyond

The CMA6 decision at the midpoint of the UAE-Belém work programme presented **a step forward towards fully operationalizing and implementing the Framework**, providing a timeline and structure for work to be conducted in 2025.

Beyond the work of the experts, the workshops, and the call for submissions on paragraph 38 of 2/CMA.5, the CMA6 decision also established the **Baku High-Level Dialogue on Adaptation**, which will be convened on the margins of each CMA session by the Presidents of that session and of the previous session, starting with CMA7.

At CMA7 and beyond, **the political and technical work of implementing the Framework** and giving life to the GGA and its targets is set to continue with the involvement of Parties and other actors.

Key topics for CMA7 will include discussion and possible adoption of an indicator package; discussion on the scope and mandate of the Baku Adaptation Roadmap; and considerations on means of implementation, paragraph 38, adaptation approaches, and the way forward beyond 2025, including the broader institutional architecture for adaptation.

Key areas of discussion and technical work for 2026 and beyond could include the following:

Operationalizing the indicators: *If CMA7 adopts an indicator package, additional work would need to be done to operationalize these indicators and make them usable by Parties. As outlined by the experts in their technical report, metadata and methodology would need to be modified for half of the indicators, while another nearly quarter of indicators are completely new and do not have existing metadata. Furthermore, for over 60% of indicators, data is only partially available, and nearly 10% do not have any data available.*

2/CMA.5 paragraph 38 (a-e) and BAR: *CMA6 launched the Baku Adaptation Roadmap (BAR) to support the implementation of elements in this paragraph. The mandate, structure, and role of the BAR will be determined by Parties at CMA7 and/or beyond, including its relation to other parts of the adaptation architecture, such as the relevant constituted bodies and processes, including the AC, LEG, NWP, and NAP process.*

Reporting on progress towards the targets: *The CMA6 decision reiterates that no additional reporting burden should be placed on Parties through implementing the Framework, and that reporting on the indicators is voluntary. It also calls on Parties to update their adaptation communications and their biennial transparency reports taking into account the Framework.*

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Organizational profile

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